

IMPACT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL MOTIVATION, COMPETENCE AND ORIENTATION ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE: A STUDY ON MSME OWNERS IN KOLLAM DISTRICT OF KERALA

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Abstract

This study addresses the relationship between entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation on organizational performance in the (Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises) MSMEs Kollam district of Kerala. Entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation is an asset especially for those who are engaged in micro, small and medium enterprises and these factors becomes a crucial value to make a good business performance. This study further classified entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation into variables such as need for achievement, self-efficacy and external environment, technical competence, marketing competence, financial competence, risk taking, proactiveness, innovation that relates to organizational performance. The sample selected by utilizing purposive sampling technique and sample size is 200 owners of small and medium organizations in Kollam district by using questionnaire. Both SPSS and MS Excel, correlation, multiple regression analysis were used for data analysis. The main findings of the study revealed that there was a positive relationship between entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation and organizational performance. The higher level of organisation performance can be achieved through three factors such as entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation. All the managerial implications will help to managers of the small and medium scale organizations to making the decisions on behalf of achieving entrepreneurial goals and objectives. The study also suggested that incorporate other variables such as characteristics of the business environment, entrepreneurial behaviour, market orientation, and other factors that affect business performance.

Keywords: “Entrepreneurial motivation”, “Entrepreneurial competence”, “Entrepreneurial orientation”, “Organizational performance” and “MSMEs”.

INTRODUCTION

The Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) is considered as the backbone of Indian economy that plays an important role in the socio-economic development of a Nation. It helps in generating employment opportunities and the development of backward and rural areas. MSME sector can lead the State economy by increasing exports through quality production techniques and products. Government and banks provides various schemes and facilities in MSME sector, targeting various social groups like SC, ST, Women, Youth, and Physically Handicapped etc.

Kerala is highly suited for the growth of the MSME sector because of its excellent connectivity, communication network, availability of highly skilled human resources, and relatively good

industrial infrastructure. The MSME sector helps in industrialization and developments of rural and backward areas, and provides employment to youth and socially disadvantaged groups such as SC, ST, women and persons with disabilities. The development of MSMEs is highly related to the economic growth of Kerala. As per the Economic Review 2020 of Government of Kerala, 13,826 new MSME units were started in Kerala in 2018-19 with a total investment of ₹1,321.94 crore, and generated employment for 49,068 persons. In 2019-20, 13,695 new MSME units were started with an investment of ₹1,338.65 crore and generated employment for 46,081 persons. The District with the largest numbers of new units started was Palakkad with 1,694 new units generating 5,984 jobs, followed by Trissur with 1,594 new MSME units generating 4,341 jobs and Ernakulam with 1,386 MSME units with 4,903 jobs. Kasaragod had the lowest number with 251 new MSME units, generating employment for 953 persons.

As per the notification, the MSMEs were reclassified on the composite criteria of investment and turnover for classification on which an enterprise shall be classified as a micro, small or medium enterprise. A micro enterprise, where the investment in plant and machinery or equipment does not exceed one crore rupees and turnover does not exceed five crore rupees, a small enterprise, where the investment in plant and machinery or equipment does not exceed ten crore rupees and turnover does not exceed fifty crore rupees; and a medium enterprise, where the investment in plant and machinery or equipment does not exceed fifty crore rupees and turnover does not exceed two hundred and fifty crore rupees.

Unfortunately, the growth in of MSMEs in entrepreneurial activity has not been fully developed due to unavailability of adequate and timely credit facility, high cost of credit, lack of modern technology, no research and innovations, insufficient training and skill development and complex labour laws. The entrepreneurial motivation and orientation of MSMEs owners helps to identifying opportunities and putting valuable ideas into practice. To improve the performance, the SMEs owners need to realize their full potential and seize any opportunities to upgrade them to become more competitive. To remain competitive, SMEs have to shift towards higher value added activities, and adopt best industry business practices.

For developing every SME business, they must have an accurate competitive strategy, one of which is entrepreneurial strategies. Various factors can be carried out by SMEs to improve their business performance. In this study focused only three factors namely entrepreneurial motivation, competence and entrepreneurial orientation which affect improving the performance of the MSME business in Kollam District of Kerala.

Entrepreneurial motivation is considered as a vital factor in improving business performance and achieving company goals. According to Suryana (2017), one of the theories to understand motivation is a process that explains the desire of a person to display specific behavior and describe the process that occurs in a person's mind, which eventually shows a specific behavior. People with high entrepreneurial motivation ability will devote all their potential and attention to managing their business well, which will increase their business performance. Al & Mostafa (2019) also states that motivation brings a convinced result in business.

Motivation is a set of forces that causes others to motivate people to behave in accordance with the interests of the organization (Moorhead & Griffin, 2010). To achieve optimal performance in business, entrepreneurs must be willing to do a good job with a high achievement motive in running their business in order to attain special competitiveness level that has bargaining position against strong competition (McClelland, 1961, 1976). Entrepreneurial motivation plays a dominant role in psychological aspects throughout entrepreneurial process and helps in high organizational performance.

Entrepreneurial competence is considered as a fundamental factor which possessed by someone who has more abilities, which differentiate from average abilities. As with other businesses, the problems faced by MSME business in Kollam District include the difficulty of developing a business due to a lack of information regarding the recent development and changes in the business environment, only relying on instinct and luck in running their business. The entrepreneurial motivation, competence and entrepreneurial orientation of MSMEs are low, so it is difficult to win in the competition when the competition is getting tighter.

Entrepreneurial competence is a set of skills and ability that possess or acquire and improve to become proactive in the business and also this is a fundamental factor possessed by someone who has more abilities, which makes him different from average abilities. The MSMEs business sectors are facing more difficulties to become success. The entrepreneurial, orientation, competence and entrepreneurial motivation of SMEs are low, so it is difficult to compete when the competition is getting tighter, so there is more guidance and skills are needed to face business competition. Echdar, (2019) states that the main requirement for a great entrepreneur is having the spirit and character of a businessman, which is influenced by skills, knowledge, and experience (competence).

In order to grow and succeed in today's rapidly changing business environment, companies regardless of their size need to constantly seek for new opportunities, possessing an entrepreneurial orientation has been recognized as potentially beneficial to the organisations. EO involves the willingness to innovate, take risks to try out new products, services and markets, and act more proactively than competitors when it comes to new opportunities in the marketplace (Covin and Slevin, 1991). Due to the potential benefits of EO, it has become a central concept in the field of entrepreneurship and received a significant role in organizational performance. Unfortunately, the research studies related on the impact of entrepreneurial motivation and orientation of SMEs towards organizational performance are very rare. Therefore, this study aims to overcome this shortcoming. The objectives of this study are to identify: (1) The impact of entrepreneurial orientation, competence, and entrepreneurial motivation partially on the business performance of the MSME business, (2) The effect of entrepreneurial orientation, competence and also the entrepreneurial motivation simultaneously on the performance of the MSME business. Besides, the result of the study is also expected can be used as input for Kollam district for and developing MSMEs business.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Entrepreneurial Motivation

Motivation is the driving force that influences a person's behavior. According to Junior (2016), motivation refers to external or internal force that moves someone to do something to achieve a certain goal.

Entrepreneurial motivation included various factors which stimulates will and desires and also activates enthusiasm in entrepreneurs for achieving their goals.

Su et al. (2020) identified the information in the social accounts of six entrepreneurs and explored the interaction between positive emotions and entrepreneurial motivation and concluded that positive emotions could affect entrepreneurial motivation and entrepreneurial process of entrepreneurs significantly.

Bartha et al. (2019) state that the main factors affecting the entrepreneurial motivation of entrepreneurs are social mission factors

Muhammad Abi Sofian, Abdul Halim, Azman Che Mat and Wan Asri Wan Abdul Aziz (2011) identified four variables in entrepreneurial motivation that relate to business performance, there are need for achievement, self-efficacy, locus of control and risk taking.

Senen Machmud and Iwan Sidharta (2016) assessed the entrepreneurial motivation, which defines both psychological variable and external environment, by measuring business performance level in Suci clothing center, Bandung and showed that entrepreneurial motivation potential simultaneously and partially have a significant influence to SMEs' business performance and the most dominant influential effect is self-efficacy while achievement has the least dominant influential effect.

Mariem Kchaich Ep and Chedli (2016) studied the importance of the intrinsic motivations that have a considerable role in the entrepreneurial decision and performance of a new firm. Thus, the study assessed there is a relationship between performance and the motivation factors. From this study concluded that there are four groups of motivations such as favorable conditions, sociological motivations, finance motivations and commercial motivations and performance can be measured by three factors such as efficacy, efficiency and effectiveness.

Entrepreneurial Competence

According to Fithri and Amanda (2012), competence is defined as the intelligence, talents, and abilities of individuals that directly affect their performance.

(Mitchelmore & Rowley, 2010) entrepreneurial competencies are seen as important to business growth and success. (Lazar & Paul, 2015) defined entrepreneurial competencies are a set of constellation or group of characteristics associated with the successful development of new business.

(Ibidunni et al., 2021) identified that entrepreneurial competencies especially organising, conceptual, learning, strategic, opportunity, and risk taking competencies are essential for achieving higher innovation performance.

Kuriloff, John M, Memphil and Dougl's Cloud (in Echdar, 2019), identified that there are four primary abilities needed to achieve an equivalent experience for successful entrepreneurship namely technical competence, marketing competence, financial competence and human relations competence.

Echdar (2019) stated that an entrepreneur in order to be able to run his business optimally and adequately, he must have at least three entrepreneurial competencies were knowledge competence, skills competence and attitude/behavior competence.

(Geril et al., 2011) identified that competencies such as efficiency orientation, planning persuasiveness, self-confidence, organizational awareness, directing others, team work, leadership and bench marketing are directed to the higher firm performance.

(Juma & Wright, 2022) found that establishing SME sustainability is the out of innovation and entrepreneurial competencies.

Entrepreneurial Orientation

Covin and selvin (1991) identified the first dimensions of EO were innovativeness, risk-taking and proactiveness.

Lumpkin and dess (1996) subsequently identified another two dimensions of EO were competitive aggressiveness and autonomy.

Krauss et al. (2005) identified two more components to this such as achievement orientation and learning orientation.

Kraus, S., Rigtering, J.P.C., Hughes, M., & Hosman, V. (2012) mentioned entrepreneurial orientation as an antecedent of growth, competitive advantage and superior performance, and prior empirical research has often shown a positive relationship between EO and performance appears to exist.

Johan Wiklund and Dean Shepherd (2005) suggested that an entrepreneurial orientation (EO) improves firm performance and found that access to capital and the dynamism of the environment are important to small businesses, and found that when combined with EO (a three-way interaction model) the configurational approach explains variance in performance over and above a contingency model (two-way interactions) and a main-effects-only model.

Kiyabo, K. and Isaga, N (2020) measured SMEs' performance using various indicators and determined the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on SMEs' performance under the mediation of competitive advantage using firm growth and personal wealth measures. Entrepreneurial orientation was adopted as an intangible resource in form of processes.

RESEARCH MODEL

This model illustrated the relationship between entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation and business performance in MSMEs owners in order to explore the correlation between three variables. In this study examined various attributes of entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation with business performance. This model divided into four sections such as entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation and business performance and assessed their relationship. Based on the literature review and previous studies, the hypotheses and conceptual framework of this study are defined as high achievement, self-efficacy, more conducive environment, technical competence, marketing competence, financial competence high risk taking ability, proactiveness and innovation are simultaneously lead to higher SMEs' business performance.

Figure 1: Frame Work

Research Hypotheses

H01: Entrepreneurial motivation does not have a significant effect on MSMEs business performance.

H02: Entrepreneurial orientation does not have a significant relationship with MSMEs business performance

To study the hypothesis stated, use multiple regression analysis as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e$$

Based on the conceptual framework the hypothesis proposed in this study are:

1. Entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation directly, have a partially positive and significant effect toward the performance of the MSMEs business.
2. Entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation simultaneously, have a positive and significant effect toward the performance of the MSMEs business.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The number of respondents was 200 owners of the MSMEs with purposive sampling methods from total of 4062 MSMEs owners which comprises of micro 3727, small 309 and medium 26 owners from kollam district of Kerala. This research employs a primary data collection method by using a standard questionnaire. Frequency, reliability, correlation and multiple regression analysis are used for data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

The profile of the respondents is shown in Table 1. The respondents are MSMEs owners from kollam district with mostly has the business period of below 5 years (n=106, 53%), followed by 5 to 10 years (n=64, 32%) and more than 10 years (n=30, 15 %). Most of the respondents have the business structure of sole proprietorship (n=156, 78%) and engaged in trading (n=96, 48%), most of respondents have micro enterprise (n=124, 62%) and the enterprises are located in rural areas (n=170, 85%)

Table 1: Profile of the respondents

Sl. No.	Variable	Attributes	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Male	154	77
		Female	46	23
2	Type of business	Manufacturing	70	35
		Trading	96	48
		Services	34	17
3	Nature of business	Micro	124	62
		Small	46	23
		Medium	30	15
4	Experience in business	Less than 5 years	106	53
		5-10	64	32
		Above 10 years	30	15
5	Number of employees	Less than 5 employee	180	90
		5 – 10 employee	20	10
		More than 10 employee	Nil	Nil
6	Business structure	Sole Proprietorship	156	78
		Partnership	44	22
7	Location	Rural	170	85
		Semi- urban	30	15

Source: Primary Data

Reliability Test

The reliability of the constructs is presented in the table no. 2. Cronbach's alpha is used for measuring internal consistency, which is, how closely related a set of items are as a group and it is considered to be a measure of scale reliability. The Cronbach's Alpha value range represents .90 and above shows excellent internal consistency and below .50 shows unacceptable. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of more than 0.60 indicates the reliability of

the instrument. As far as the data presented by below table entrepreneurial motivation is properly measured by the three variables such as need for achievement, self-efficacy and environment. Five items included in the need for achievement and self-efficacy and four items in environment. The alpha coefficient is .808 and suggesting that the items have relatively high internal consistency. Entrepreneurial competence is measured by using three variables such as technical competence, marketing competence, financial competence and the alpha coefficient is .726 which is considered as reliable. Entrepreneurial orientation is also measured by three variables such as innovation, risk taking and proactiveness. Three items included in innovation and four items each in risk taking and proactiveness. The alpha coefficient is .798 and suggesting that the items have relatively highly acceptable. The variable business performance is measured by using 5 items and alpha coefficient is .882 which is acceptable. Based on the results, the questionnaire can be used as a measuring tool for collecting data in this study.

Table: 2: Reliability of the constructs

Variable	No of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
1. Entrepreneurial motivation	5	0.808
2. Entrepreneurial competence	3	0.726
3. Entrepreneurial orientation	3	0.798
4. Business performance	5	0.882

Source: Primary Data

Multiple Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is conducted to find out the cause and effect relationship between entrepreneurial motivation, competence, orientation and business performance both partially and simultaneously. (Table 3)

Table 3: Regression Model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.563	.360		4.342	.000
	Entrepreneurial motivation	.017	.008	.158	2.186	.030
	Entrepreneurial competence	.020	.008	.186	2.595	.010
	Entrepreneurial Orientation	.019	.009	.299	2.071	.040
a. Dependent Variable: Business performance						

Independent variables of the model

Three factors were used to develop the model with regard to the study objective. These variables include;

- X1 – Entrepreneurial motivation
- X2 – Entrepreneurial competence
- X3 – Entrepreneurial orientation

These three independent variables are determined each by a set of statements measured on a Likert scale pooling different expediencies. This was done by combining the positive scores (strongly agree + agree) for each of the four independent variables’ statements or attributes to change the variables to dummy taking values 1 and 0.

The regression equation model is described in the form of the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Business performance} = & 1.563 \\ & +.017 \text{ Entrepreneurial motivation} \\ & +.020 \text{ Entrepreneurial competence} \\ & +.019 \text{ Entrepreneurial orientation} \\ & + \text{ Error Term} \end{aligned}$$

The explanation of the regression equation is as follows:

- The regression co-efficient of the entrepreneurial motivation variable (X1) has a positive direction in its effect on the business performance of MSMEs(Y)
- The regression co-efficient of the entrepreneurial competence variable (X2) has a positive direction in its effect on the business performance of MSMEs(Y)
- The regression co-efficient of the entrepreneurial orientation variable (X3) has a positive direction in its effect on the business performance of MSMEs(Y)

Hypotheses Tests Analysis

1. F test(Simultaneous test)

The effect of independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) can be seen in the table 4:

Table 4 Simultaneous Regression Table

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	63.981	3	21.327	14.199	.000 ^b
	Residual	294.399	196	1.502		
	Total	358.380	199			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Entrepreneurial motivation, Entrepreneurial competence, Entrepreneurial Orientation,						
b. Dependent Variable: Business performance						

Based on the results of the analysis, table 4 shows the value of F count = 14.199 with a significant of .0000 <.05 it shows that simultaneously, Entrepreneurial motivation, Entrepreneurial competence and Entrepreneurial Orientation effect toward the business performance of MSMEs shops in Kollam district have a positive and significant effect.

2. The t-test (partial test)

The requirement for the significance of the partial effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) based on the t test value is if t value > of t table value. The significance is less than $\alpha = 0.05$, so the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected and alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted. It indicates that statistically, the effect of entrepreneurial motivation(X1), entrepreneurial competence (X2), and entrepreneurial orientation (X3) partially has a significant effect toward the business performance of the MSMEs (Y).

3. Determination Coefficient Test

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	0.901	0.82	0.78.

The study established R_ squared=0.82 and adjusted R_ squared= 0.78, which means that influence on the business performance of MSMEs Shops (Y), as indicated by the R Square value of 0.82 or 82%. The 82% of the MSMEs shop business performance's variable (Y) is influenced by the independent variables of Entrepreneurial Competence (X1), Market Orientation (X2), and Entrepreneurial Motivation (X3) and the remaining 18% is caused by other factors not considered in this study. The hypothesis is statistically proved and states that entrepreneurial motivation competence and orientation simultaneously have a significant effect toward the performance of the MSMEs business.

Summary

1. Entrepreneurial motivation positively and significantly effects on the MSMEs Business Performance

The finding confirms that the entrepreneurial motivation had a positive and substantial impact toward MSMEs business performance in kollam district of Kerala. The t-test value of the entrepreneurial motivation variable (X1) is 2.186 this is more than t table value. With a P value of 0.030; probability of rejecting a correct null hypothesis is less than 0.05 so H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted, which means that the influence of entrepreneurial motivation (X1) has a significant effect toward the MSMEs business performance (Y). Entrepreneurial competence positively and significantly effects on the MSMEs Business Performance. This result is similar to the study of Wisda Apriana's (2013 which concluded that Motivation, Managerial Ability, Competence, and Environment simultaneously and significantly effect on the Business Performance of Street Vendors in Bekasi.

2. Entrepreneurial competence positively and significantly effects on the MSMEs Business Performance

Entrepreneurial competence brings a positive and substantial effect on the MSMEs business's performance in kollam district. From the results of analysis the t value of entrepreneurial competence (X2) is 2.595 this is more than the t table value which shows that the influence of

entrepreneurial competence (X2) significantly affect toward the performance of the MSMEs business performance (Y). Thus, each change in the entrepreneurial competence variable (X2) of 1 contributes to the increase in the business performance (Y) by 2.595. Thus it can be concluded that entrepreneurial competence (X2) has a significant effect toward the performance of the MSMEs business performance (Y) with a P value of 0.010; probability of rejecting a correct null hypothesis is less than 0.005. This result is similar to the study of Nina Marlina (2013) which shows that entrepreneurial competence and market orientation simultaneously effect on the business performance of the Paris Van Java Doll SME Center in Bandung.

3. Entrepreneurial orientation positively and significantly effects on the MSMEs Business Performance

Entrepreneurial orientation brings a positive and substantial effect on the MSMEs business's performance in Kollam district. From the results of analysis the t value of entrepreneurial orientation (X3) is 2.071 this is more than the t table value which shows that the influence of entrepreneurial orientation (X3) significantly affect toward the performance of the MSMEs business performance (Y). Thus, each change in the entrepreneurial orientation variable (X3) of 1 contributes to the increase in the business performance (Y) by 2.071. With a P value of 0.040; probability of rejecting a correct null hypothesis is less than 0.005 hence the alternative hypothesis is acquired and the conclusion that entrepreneurial orientation (X3) has a significant effect toward the performance of the MSMEs business performance (Y). This result is similar to the study Singh .S (2008) which shows that the components of entrepreneurial orientation such as marketing, social and economic orientation had a positive impact on business performance.

4. Entrepreneurial motivation, Competence, and orientation have A positive and Significant Effect Simultaneously On the Business Performance of MSMEs

Entrepreneurial motivation (X1), entrepreneurial competence (X2), and Entrepreneurial orientation (X3) have a positive and significant effect simultaneously on the Business Performance of MSMEs S (Y) in Kollam District of Kerala. The magnitude of the simultaneous variable contribution to the MSMEs business performance (Y) is shown by the R Square value of 0.82 or 82%, which concluded that about 82% of the MSMEs business performance variables (Y) are influenced by the independent variables of Entrepreneurial motivation (X1), Entrepreneurial competence (X2), and Entrepreneurial Orientation (X3). In comparison, the remaining 7.6% is caused by other factors.

CONCLUSION

The main objective was to examine the relationship between entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation and MSMEs business performance. Entrepreneurial motivation is measured under three sub variables namely, need for achievement, self-efficacy and external environment, entrepreneurial competence are measured with the components such as technical competence, marketing competence and financial competence and entrepreneurial orientation

is measured under three sub variables like innovativeness, proactiveness and risk taking of MSMEs owners in kollam district of Kerala. The findings of the study revealed that entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation have a positive and significant impact on business performance of MSMEs. It is concluded that the achievement, risk propensity, self-efficacy, enhanced external environment, technical competence, marketing competence and financial competence, risk taking ability, innovation and proactiveness will contribute to improve the business performance of the entrepreneurs of MSMEs. This means that the high level of business performance can be achieved with high attention of entrepreneurial motivation, competence and orientation factors. Further researches are suggested to incorporate other variables such as characteristics of the business environment, entrepreneurial behaviour, market orientation, and other factors that affect business performance.

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